

Research on the Impact of Short-Form Video Advertising on Social Media on the Purchase Intention of Gen Z in Vietnam

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pham Van Tuan^{1*}, Le Anh Chan², Dinh Tran Ngoc Huy³, Nguyen Quang Anh⁴, Pham Chau Giang⁵, Nguyen Quynh Trang⁶ & Nguyen Phuong Uyen⁷

^{1,2,4,5,6,7}National Economics University, 207 Giai Phong, Dong Tam, Hanoi, Vietnam.

³Banking University HCM city Vietnam - International University of Japan, Japan.

Corresponding Author (Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pham Van Tuan) - phamvantuan@neu.edu.vn*

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.46382/MJBAS.2023.7104>

Copyright: © 2023 Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pham Van Tuan et al. This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Article Received: 14 December 2022

Article Accepted: 26 January 2023

Article Published: 21 February 2023

ABSTRACT

In recent years, short-form video has become a popular form of advertising on social media. The way consumers make decisions to purchase has changed owing to this new marketing method. This study aims to investigate the impact of informativeness, entertainment, credibility, social interaction, incentives and irritation of short-form video advertising on social media on the purchase intention of Gen Z in Vietnam through user attitude and advertising value. A survey was conducted by collecting responses from 1257 respondents who are Gen Z and familiar with social media, which was later analysed using SmartPLS. The findings revealed that advertising value and user attitude significantly affect customers' purchase intention. In addition, advertising value is directly affected by informativeness, entertainment and credibility. Meanwhile, user attitude is directly affected by social interaction, incentives and irritation. Finally, the research team propose some solutions for businesses to increase the purchase intention of Gen Z in Vietnam through short-form video advertising on social media.

Keywords: Short-form video advertising; Social media; Purchase intention; Gen Z.

EST 1892

LSBU

YNU

1. Introduction

Recent technological advancements have transformed advertising into a multifaceted, dynamic medium with tremendous potential for development (Boone et al., 2007). The short video market has been heating up and growing quickly in recent years. Recently, short films in particular have taken over many digital markets and e-commerce sites (Addo, Dorgbefu Jnr. et al., 2021). Businesses are relying on the appealing features of online short video advertising to establish brands and provide around-the-clock shopping experiences to customers, which directly impacts consumers' purchase intentions (Addo, Fang et al., 2021; Molinillo et al., 2019).

Researchers have previously investigated the link between brief video advertisements and customer behaviour and discovered a variety of contributing elements. The primary research topic in this study are Gen Z consumer groups – who born in 1997 – 2006, a customer base that has not been explored in previous studies and the value features of mobile short video commercials. This study sought to examine how new possible characteristics of short video advertisements could affect young customers' psychological pleasure. Besides, it also investigated how it influences consumption willingness, leading to the construction of a new theoretical model of online consumption suitable to the young consumers in the era of mobile Internet. This not only supplements and enriches the existing advertising theoretical models, but also provides a reference for the innovation and sustainable development of

mobile short video advertising in the Internet era and injects new vitality into the sustainable development of the consumer economy in the post-pandemic era.

2. Theoretical foundation

2.1. Theory of Planned Behaviour

Predicting deliberate and planned behaviour is the Theory of Planned Behaviour's (Ajzen, 1991) main goal. Different from the TRA which only examines two main factors influencing intention are personal attitudes toward behaviour and subjective norms (Ajzen, 1991), the TPB suggested that an individual's behaviour is a function of three types of beliefs: (1) behavioural beliefs (Attitude toward Behaviour), which refer to their opinions about the likely results of a behaviour; (2) normative beliefs (Subjective Norm), which refer to their opinions about the expectations of important people; and (3) control beliefs (Perceived Behavioural Control), which refer to their opinions about the absence or presence of factors that might facilitate behaviour (Ajzen, 1991).

2.2. Short form video advertising

Since the short video has just developed in recent years, the shape is different and the speed of change is very fast, so the current academic community does not have a clear definition of the concept of short-form video. At present, the definition of short video mainly includes the following: (1) Short video refers to a new type of real-time video-sharing form that is recorded, edited, and uploaded on some special short video platforms with seconds as the counting unit, and the audience plays on this platform. (2) Short video is different from long video; in that, it is played on new media, which is more convenient for dissemination and sharing, and the duration is usually within 5 minutes. (3) A short video, in its strictest and traditional sense, is any video that does not exceed a ten-minute duration. (4) Short video refers to a new video format in which the video content is shorter than 15 minutes, which is more spread and photographed by Internet mobile intelligent terminals, beautified and edited by Internet mobile intelligent terminals, and the video is shared to social media platforms in real-time.

2.3. Research on effects of short videos on purchase intention

Purchase intention indicates likelihood that consumers will plan or be willing to purchase a certain product or service in the future (Wu et al., 2011). If consumers have a positive purchase intention, then a positive brand engagement will promote that purchase (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975; Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007). As short video advertising occupies an increasing proportion of commercial advertising (Krämer et al., 2019), the correlation between mobile short video advertising and consumer buying behaviour has been investigated from different dimensions. Wei Jingqiu et al. (2020) found that users like to browse the short video mainly because of its serviceability, entertainment, and usability. These factors will directly affect customers' emotional experience and thus stimulate their purchase intention and behaviour. Wang Xiangning (2020) concluded that users will be more willing to buy a brand after they develop a closer relationship with this brand under the effect of short video contents. Besides, such contents are more influential than those from the traditional advertisement in aspects of entertainment, function, and social interaction, and these factors also affect customers' purchase intention. In the context of social media, short video advertisements influence consumers' emotional experience through

entertaining and valuable information, thus generating various interactive participation and purchase behaviours. By comprehensively observing such users' motivations, likes, dislikes and lifestyles, Zhang Tianli et al. (2019) found that many of them are pursuing "energy, connection and individuation", showing the characteristics of group image. The characteristics of Internet celebrities and their opinions also significantly improve the intentions and attitudes of consumers (Liu et al., 2019). Meng et al. (2020) found that the information source characteristics of Internet celebrities have an impact on arousing the search and purchase behaviours of consumers. Wang B. et al. (2020) believed that the design and presentation of short video advertisements should focus on user experience to meet psychological needs and thus improve the consumption willingness of consumers. By accurate implantation into different fragmented periods of consumers, it can build product brand image through long duration and repetitive play to stimulate the desire of consumers to buy.

3. Hypotheses and Conceptual model

3.1. Informativeness

Informativeness acts as an important predictor of an advertisement's value (Dwinanda, B., Syaripuddin, F. A., Hudaifi, & Hendriana, E., 2022). Information is a crucial aspect of social media advertising because potential customers frequently want more information about the product (Nguyen Duy Thanh et al., 2013).

H1: Perceived social interactivity of short-form video advertising is positively associated with perceived advertising value.

3.2. Equations

H2: Perceived entertainment of short-form video advertising is positively associated with perceived advertising value.

3.3. Credibility

H3: Perceived credibility of short-form video advertising is positively associated with perceived advertising value.

3.4. Social interactivity

H4: Perceived social interactivity of short-form video advertising is positively associated with perceived user attitude.

3.5. Incentives

H5: Perceived incentives of short-form video advertising is positively associated with perceived user attitude.

3.6. Irritation

H6: Perceived irritation of short-form video advertising is negatively associated with perceived user attitude.

3.7. Advertising value

H7: Perceived advertising value of short-form video advertising is positively associated with purchase intention.

3.8. User attitude

According to research on mobile advertising in China, attitude is the key element in purchasing decisions that can be used to predict online purchases (Xu D.J., 2016). The relationship is stated as follow:

H8: Perceived user attitude of short-form video advertising is positively associated with purchase intention.

From the research hypotheses mentioned above, the authors propose a proposed research model as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual model

4. Methodology

The study was conducted using both qualitative and quantitative methods. Qualitative method uses document collection techniques, desk research to determine the factors of short-form video that affect consumers' purchase intention, on that basis builds hypotheses and overall model.

5. Results

The group author first creates statistical data with 1257 respondents for 9 factors, including 4 demographic variables, 4 variables related to short-form advertisement, and variable Video Length. To test our hypothesis research model, we use the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) method because of its suitability for complex structural models that include many constructs, indicators and/or model relationships (Hair et al., 2019). In the partial least square method, the structure model is estimated by an iterative method, which strengthens the relationship between independent variables and dependent variables (S. Hosany and Martin, 2012). Additionally, the PLS approach exhibits greater convergence in its simplicity and places fewer restrictions on data normality (Chin et al., 2003). As a result, SmartPLS software was employed and the PLS analysis was appropriate for this research.

5.1. Sampling

Table 1. Demographics of respondents

		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	457	36.4
	Female	800	63.6

	16 – 18	251	20
Age	19 – 22	567	45.1
	23 – 25	439	34.9
	University	480	38.2
Education	High School	241	19.2
	Graduate	212	16.9
	Intermediate college	324	25.8
	No income	332	26.4
Monthly income (VND)	Over 10 million	184	14.6
	1 - 3 million	354	28.2
	3 - 6 million	185	14.7
	6 - 10 million	202	16.1
	Less than 2 hours	222	17.7
Time spent on social media/day	Over 8 hours	109	8.7
	From 5-8 hours	241	19.2
	From 2 to 5 hours	685	54.5
	1 - 5 times/day	447	35.6
Frequency encounter short-form video	6 - 10 times/day	427	34
	More than 10 times	383	30.5
	Cuisine	1810	36
Frequently watched advertising content	Health care	1002	19.9
	Houseware	703	14
	Fashion	1052	20.9
	Others	461	9.2

	Less than 15 seconds	576	45.8
	From 1 minute to less than 2 minutes	74	5.9
Video length	From 15 to under 30 seconds	427	34
	From 2 minutes to 3 minutes	18	1.4
	From 30 seconds to less than 1 minute	162	12.9
Type of short-form video ads	Skippable short-form video ads	739	58.8
	Non-skippable short-form video ads	518	41.2

SOURCE: Authors' compilation from data processing

From the collected data, the respondents for the survey primarily are female, at about 63.6% of the total. Additionally, the respondents are mostly among young Gens in the age of 19-25. In terms of educational attainment, most of the participants are students studying at universities and colleges, which explains the low monthly income (54.6% have income below 3 million VND), mainly due to student status (see Table 1).

Some moderating variables examined in this research served as further analysis of Gen Z social media usage behaviours as well as their experiences regarding short-form video advertisement.

The data shows that Gen Z spends 2–5 hours on different social media per day. It can also be concluded that internet users can encounter short video ads with a frequency that fluctuates strongly, depending on the duration of their social network use. A total of 36% of consumers view advertisements featuring food-related material. A significant portion of respondents (around 20% of respondents each) are seen viewing social media advertising for both healthcare and fashion material. Besides, social media users are more likely to encounter short skippable ads than non-skippable ads. Finally, Facebook is still the most popular platform for Gen Z to get exposed to short-form video advertisements followed by Instagram. TikTok was expected to have a huge impact on Gen Z short-form video-watching habits, however, the data shows when it comes to advertisement density, TikTok accounts for 30% which is less than Facebook.

Regarding the variable Video Length, most respondents encounter 15 – second advertisements and more than 80% of respondents say that they watch under 30 seconds. Understandably, since advertisements under 30 seconds can hold viewers' attention while also having interesting and visually appealing information, individuals are more likely to encounter this sort of advertisement.

5.2. Reliability and Validity

5.2.1. Evaluating Measurement Model

We see:

Table 2. Construct Reliability and Validity

Variable	Item	Factor Loading	Mean	S.D	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	AVE
Irritation	IRR1	0.709	2.581	0.814	0.801	0.868	0.624
	IRR2	0.874	2.609	0.771			
	IRR3	0.801	2.698	0.7			
	IRR4	0.765	2.574	0.85			
Incentives	INC1	0.914	3.389	0.878	0.879	0.925	0.804
	INC2	0.863	3.453	0.74			
	INC3	0.912	3.331	0.833			
Credibility	CRE1	0.871	3.459	0.776	0.858	0.903	0.701
	CRE2	0.831	3.411	0.754			
	CRE3	0.839	3.353	0.773			
	CRE4	0.806	3.259	0.835			
Social Interactivity	SI1	0.787	3.267	0.696	0.898	0.922	0.664
	SI2	0.846	3.268	0.816			
	SI3	0.792	3.379	0.707			
	SI4	0.828	3.341	0.811			
	SI5	0.762	3.442	0.794			
	SI6	0.869	3.256	0.899			
Informativeness	INF1	0.864	3.39	0.709	0.896	0.928	0.763
	INF2	0.85	3.243	0.811			

	INF3	0.901	3.373	0.734			
	INF4	0.877	3.374	0.855			
	ENT1	0.702	3.512	0.675			
	ENT2	0.875	3.416	0.834			
Entertainment	ENT3	0.866	3.387	0.718	0.878	0.91	0.669
	ENT4	0.792	3.433	0.815			
	ENT5	0.843	3.397	0.752			
	AV1	0.891	3.126	0.897			
Advertising Value	AV2	0.851	3.286	0.756	0.891	0.924	0.753
	AV3	0.869	3.332	0.781			
	AV4	0.861	3.329	0.74			
	ATT1	0.873	3.2	0.783			
	ATT2	0.831	3.368	0.753			
User Attitude	ATT3	0.803	3.278	0.849	0.891	0.92	0.697
	ATT4	0.771	3.317	0.777			
	ATT5	0.890	3.391	0.827			
	PI1	0.815	3.311	0.904			
	PI2	0.771	3.303	0.804			
Purchase Intention	PI3	0.839	3.421	0.779	0.892	0.921	0.7
	PI4	0.878	3.397	0.726			
	PI5	0.876	3.416	0.787			

SOURCE: Authors' compilation from data processing

An item's factor loading indicates how effectively it represents the underlying construct. The factor loading in the observation is all over 0.70 which is considered the ideal standard according to Vinzi, Chin, Henseler, and Wang (2010). For the composite reliability criterion, higher value denotes a higher reliability level. Previous researchers consider values between 0.60 and 0.70 as "acceptable in exploratory research," while results between 0.70 and

0.95 represent “satisfactory to good” reliability levels (Hair et al. 2017b, p. 112). On the other hand, if the values that are too high, such as those above 0.95, pose a challenge because they imply that the items are almost identical and redundant. With the CR’s value ranging from 0.868 to 0.928, this data proved high reliability levels. Cronbach's Alpha is another internal consistency reliability measure that uses the same assumptions as composite reliability but produces lower values. An acceptable threshold for the AVE is 0.70 or higher. All Cronbach's Alpha values in the research are above 0.8 which indicates that, on average, the construct explains (more than) 50% of the variance of its items. Convergent validity, also known as communality, is measured by the average variance extracted (AVE) across all items linked to a specific construct. According to Fornell and Larcker (1981), $AVE \geq 0.5$ confirms the convergent validity and all the AVE values in Table are greater or equal to 0.5.

Table 3. Discriminant validity

	ATT	AV	CRE	ENT	INC	INF	IRR	PI	SI
ATT									
AV	0.099								
CRE	0.081	0.639							
ENT	0.081	0.475	0.368						
INC	0.679	0.165	0.17	0.158					
INF	0.05	0.556	0.384	0.485	0.141				
IRR	0.479	0.138	0.163	0.233	0.35	0.121			
PI	0.273	0.643	0.361	0.269	0.243	0.344	0.065		
SI	0.484	0.074	0.1	0.092	0.358	0.089	0.462	0.155	

SOURCE: Authors' compilation from data processing

The discriminant validity is based on the multitrait-multimethod matrix, to assess discriminant validity: the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) (Henseler et al., 2015) is chosen in our study. As the ratios were all below 0.679, they met the strictest requirement for discriminant validity (less than 0.85), suggesting they could be used safely in the subsequent analysis.

5.2.2. Evaluating Structure Model

Table 4. Results of hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Path	VIF	Beta	T Statistics	P Values	Result
H1	INF → AV	1.323	0.280	10.18	0	Supported
H2	ENT → AV	1.327	0.178	7.113	0	Supported
H3	CRE → AV	1.194	0.403	16.863	0	Supported

H4	SI → ATT	1.239	0.208	8.461	0	Supported
H5	INC → ATT	1.167	0.486	20.199	0	Supported
H6	IRR → ATT	1.236	-0.191	7.955	0	Supported
H7	AV → PI	1.001	0.580	22.777	0	Supported
H8	ATT → PI	1.001	0.259	9.743	0	Supported

SOURCE: Authors' compilation from data processing

6. Discussions

The study is one of the initial empirical investigations done in an Asian country. It is anticipated that short video advertising will have a large impact on young consumers worldwide since it is one of the advertising formats that greatly influences consumer attitudes and intentions. The study has produced some fresh findings that may help with future research in a bigger field, like food. Although several studies on the advertising business have been conducted to date, this research is one of the few that genuinely focuses on the experience of short video advertising in emerging nations.

7. Limitations and Further Research

Future studies may use longitudinal research methods to study the impact of short-form video advertising on social media on people's purchase intention, as the results of research may be affected by future technology and changing social media platforms. Finally, although we believe the study model is sufficient to inspect the impact of short-form video advertising on social media on the purchase intention of Gen Z in Vietnam, there are still other influencing factors.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Acknowledgement

Thank you editors and friends who assisted this publication.

References

[1] Aaker, D. A., & Bruzzone, D. E. (1985). Causes of irritation in advertising. *Journal of marketing*, 49(2), 47-57.

- [2] Azar, S. L., Machado, J. C., Vacas-de-Carvalho, L., & Mendes, A. (2016). Motivations to interact with brands on Facebook—Towards a typology of consumer–brand interactions. *Journal of Brand Management*, 23(2), 153-178.
- [3] Bamoriya, H. (2012). SMS Advertising in India: is tam A robust Model for explaining intention? *Acta Universitatis Danubius, Economica*, 8(3), 17-27.
- [4] Bendixen, M. T. (1993). Advertising effects and effectiveness. *European journal of marketing*, 27(10), 19-32.
- [5] Cho, S., Huh, J., & Faber, R. J. (2014). The influence of sender trust and advertiser trust on multistage effects of viral advertising. *Journal of advertising*, 43(1), 100-114.
- [6] Dehghani, M., Niaki, M. K., Ramezani, I., & Sali, R. (2016). Evaluating the influence of YouTube advertising for attraction of young customers. *Computers in human behaviour*, 59, 165-172.
- [7] Dimock, M. (2019). Defining generations: Where Millennials end and Generation Z begins. *Pew Research Center*, 17(1), 1-7.
- [8] Djafarova, E., & Rushworth, C. (2017). Exploring the credibility of online celebrities' Instagram profiles in influencing the purchase decisions of young female users. *Computers in human behaviour*, 68, 1-7.
- [9] DTN Huy, NT Hang, NT Dung. (2021). Marketing Strategy based on Competitor Analysis-A Case in Vietnam Medicine Sector, *Revista Geintec-Gestao Inovacao E Tecnologias*, 11(3), 103-111.
- [10] Ducoffe, R. H. (1996). Advertising value and advertising on the web-Blog@management. *Journal of advertising research*, 36(5), 21-32.
- [11] Dwinanda, B., Syaripuddin, F. A., & Hendriana, E. (2022). Examining the extended advertising value model: A case of TikTok short video ads. *Mediterranean Journal of Social & Behavioral Research*, 6(2), 35-44.
- [12] Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics.
- [13] Hair Jr., J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2021). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications.
- [14] Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European business review*, 31(1), 2-24.
- [15] Hanley, M., Becker, M., & Martinsen, J. (2006). Factors influencing mobile advertising acceptance: will incentives motivate college students to accept mobile advertisements. *International Journal of Mobile Marketing*, 1(1), 50-58.
- [16] Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modelling. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 43, 115-135.
- [17] Hunt, H., Rotzoll, Kim, J. Haefner, C. Sandage. (2013). Advertising in Contemporary Society: Perspectives toward Understanding. Columbus: Grid,1976. *Journal of Advertising*, 6(3), 44-45.

- [18] Huong, P. T. L., & Minh, T. N. P. (2020). Cac nhan to anh huong den thai do cua nguoi tieu dung tre doi voi quang cao SMS. Tap chi Phat trien Kinh te, 89-108.
- [19] Huyen, D. T. L. (2017). Nghien cuu yeu to anh huong va he qua cua cam nhan bi lam phien trong quang cao truc tuyen. Tap Chi Khoa Hoc Dai Hoc Mo Thanh Pho Ho Chi Minh-Kinh Te Va Quan Tri Kinh Doanh, 12(3), 129-143.
- [20] Iddris, F. (2006). Mobile advertising in B2C marketing.
- [21] Kim, Y. J., & Han, J. (2014). Why smartphone advertising attracts customers: A model of Web advertising, flow, and personalization. Computers in human behaviour, 33, 256-269.
- [22] LT Hue, NT Thuy, DTN Huy, NV Binh, DTT Huyen, NTM Thao. (2020). Factors affecting the access to bank credit of SMEs in northeastern region, Vietnam, International Journal of Entrepreneurship, 24, 1-12.
- [23] Martins, J., Costa, C., Oliveira, T., Gonoalves, R., & Branco, F. (2019). How smartphone advertising influences consumers' purchase intention. Journal of Business Research, 94, 378-387.
- [24] Mir, I. A., & Rehman, K. (2013). Factors affecting consumer attitudes and intentions toward user-generated product content on YouTube. Management & Marketing, 8(4).
- [25] N Nga, P Tuan, D Huy, D Huong. (2021). Relationship between Competitor-based Marketing Mix Strategies and Production Activities in Manufacturing and Renewable Energy Companies, Advances in Mechanics, 9(3), 1367-1378.
- [26] ND Trung, DTN Huy, P Van Tuan, DT Huong. (2021). ICT and digital tech effects on marketing strategies and choosing competitor affecting on business operation-A case in hotel and entertainment sector, Design Engineering, 7, 8437-8449.
- [27] NTT Phuong, DTN Huy, P Van Tuan. (2020). The evaluation of impacts of a seven factor model on nvb stock.
- [28] Oanh, N. D. Y., & An, Q. L. X. (2018). Thai do doi voi quang cao truc tuyen va y dinh tiep tục mua của người tiêu dùng: Mot nghien cuu trong ngành hàng tiêu dùng nhanh. Tap Chi Khoa Hoc Dai Hoc Mo Thanh Pho Ho Chi Minh-Kinh Te Va Quan Tri Kinh Doanh, 13(2), 116-136.
- [29] O'Reilly, K., & Marx, S. (2011). How young, technical consumers assess online WOM credibility. Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal, 14(4), 330-359.
- [30] P Van Tuan, DTN Huy, MBANT Hoa, DT Huong. (2021). Technology Applications, IT Effects on Marketing and Role of Digital Marketing in Stock Investment Industry-and Industrial Competitors Impacts on Business Risk Level, Design Engineering, 1828-1843.
- [31] P Van Tuan, DTN Huy, ND Trung, NT Hoa. (2021). Marketing Strategies for Tourism and Digital Tech Applications in Tourism Industry-A Case of Och Tourism Corporation in Vietnam, Design Engineering, 7.
- [32] Sarılgan, A. E., Şahap, A. K. A. N., Bakır, M., & Süleç, H. (2022). The impact of advertising creativity on purchase intention in the airline industry: A stimulus-organism-response (SOR) perspective. European Journal of Tourism Research, 30, 3014-3014.

- [33] Shatto, B., & Erwin, K. (2016). Moving on from Millennials: Preparing for generation Z. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 47(6), 253-254.
- [34] Thanh, N. D., Nghia, T. D., & Cuong, P. M. (2013). De xuất mô hình chấp nhận quảng cáo trực tuyến trên mạng xã hội ở Việt Nam. *Tap chí Phát triển Khoa học và Công nghệ*, 16, 5-19.
- [35] PM Dat, DTN Huy (2021). Management Issues in Medical Industry in Vietnam, *Management* 25(1), 141-154.
- [36] P Van Tuan, DTN Huy, MBANT Hoa, DT Huong. (2021). Technology Applications, IT Effects on Marketing and Role of Digital Marketing In Stock Investment Industry-And Industrial Competitors Impacts on Business Risk Level, *Design engineering*, 1828-1843.
- [37] P Anh, DTN Huy. (2021). Internet benefits and digital transformation applying in boosting tourism sector and forecasting tourism management revenue, *Management*.
- [38] Varshney, U. (2003). Location management for mobile commerce applications in wireless internet environment. *ACM Transactions on Internet Technology (TOIT)*, 3(3), 236-255.
- [39] Vinzi, V. E., Chin, W. W., Henseler, J., & Wang, H. (2010). *Handbook of partial least squares: Concepts. Springer Science & Business Media: Methods and Applications.*
- [40] Wang, S. L., & Lan, N. T. N. (2018). A study on the attitude of customer towards viral video advertising on social media: A case study in Viet Nam. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*, 7(6), 54-60.
- [41] Xu, D. J. (2006). The influence of personalization in affecting consumer attitudes toward mobile advertising in China. *Journal of computer information systems*, 47(2), 9-19.
- [42] Zhao, J., & Wang, J. (2020). Health advertising on short-video social media: A study on user attitudes based on the extended technology acceptance model. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(5), 1501.